

ECONOMY

METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK FOR ASSESSING ENTERPRISE COMPETITIVENESS

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Abstract

This study synthesizes various theoretical perspectives on competition, highlighting it as an intrinsic economic phenomenon related to market exchange mechanisms for goods and services. It identifies vital aspects for evaluating the formation prerequisites of competitiveness – specifically competitive, product-based, and outcome-oriented factors. The characteristics of the methodological framework for assessing enterprise competitiveness are substantiated, and essential criteria for creating a comprehensive and reliable competitiveness assessment set are established.

Keywords: competition, enterprise, competitiveness, competitive advantage, market mechanism.

Introduction. Competitive rivalry is an integral element of the market mechanism, serving as a crucial factor for continuously enhancing business efficiency and improving commercial and economic relations within the market context. Competition is the primary mechanism that ensures a market economy's effectiveness, balance, and dynamism, playing a pivotal role in shaping global economic relations amid the contemporary globalization of all aspects of societal development.

Competition (derived from the Latin «concur», «concurrentia» - collision or confrontation) is one of the essential conditions and significant drivers of societal, economic development. It serves as the principal force behind the expanded reproduction of production and the effective self-regulation of economic relations. Free competition, in particular, amplifies the role and importance of the individual within the broader context of social development, offering extensive opportunities for personal expression and establishing equal conditions for realizing individual ambitions and needs. The growth of market competition, which fosters genuine partnerships between consumers and leading enterprises, invariably leads to quality improvements and price reductions for goods. Ultimately, this progression benefits society, transcending geographical, political, and national boundaries.

Literature Review. The theoretical and methodological foundations for determining enterprise competitiveness have been explored in the works of distinguished economists, including Arefyeva O. [1], Horbal N. [4], Dashko I. [2], Dykany V. [3], Kuzmin O. [4], Lutska T. [1], Ponomaryova T. [3], Tarnavska N. [5], Camp R. [6], Kotler P. [8], Lane K. [8], Lenskold J. [7], Warren K. [9], among others. However, certain facets of competitiveness assessment (particularly those addressing the nuances of competitive development within specific market conditions) remain insufficiently studied. This underscores the urgent need for further investigation in these areas.

This study aims to synthesize theoretical perspectives and advance the methodological framework for assessing enterprise competitiveness.

Research Findings. Competition is an inseparable element of market relations, acting as an external force that compels producers to continually enhance the

efficiency of their economic activities, expand production scales, accelerate scientific and technological progress, and pursue the adoption of cutting-edge technologies and organizational forms in production. It represents the rivalry among market participants over optimal conditions for producing, selling, and purchasing goods and services and, consequently, maximizing profits.

For competitive rivalry to effectively foster market development, certain conditions must be met: a substantial number of sellers, comprehensive information about products and their sale conditions, the mobility of production resources.

When these conditions are fulfilled, market competition, which leads to the equalization of profit margins among producers, will facilitate the optimal allocation of labor and capital across production sectors. Thus, competitive market relations become the primary domain for the manifestation of the law of value, a principle in economics that states that the value of a commodity is determined by the amount of socially necessary labor time required to produce it. This law ensures both material (production of consumer value aligning with demand structure) and financial (alignment of aggregate product values, i.e., the sum of goods prices with the volume of effective demand) equilibrium in economic development.

Thus, two primary aspects of competition emerge as an economic phenomenon intrinsic to the functioning of the market mechanism for the exchange of goods and services:

1. Reflexive Nature of Competitive Interaction – This approach emphasizes the reflexive-behavioral dynamics among market participants (sellers and buyers), manifesting in varied forms of rivalry for advantageous access to specific resources, goods, and services that are objects of market exchange. This reflexive-behavioral perspective highlights participants' diverse strategies in securing optimal market interaction conditions.

2. Optimization-Based Selection of Market Participants – Here, competition functions as a process of "natural" selection (grounded in self-regulating mechanisms), favoring entities capable of offering the most beneficial conditions for society in producing and consuming goods and services essential to meeting human needs. This socially selective perspective sees market

competition as privileging participants who best meet efficient production and consumer satisfaction criteria.

It is essential to underscore that, for individual market participants, the critical elements of competition are often directly tied to the specific conditions and circumstances of their involvement in competitive (reflexive) interactions. Conversely, for society as a whole, competition acts as an automated mechanism for economic development, selecting the most efficient means (especially in terms of the ratio of results to costs) to meet a broad range of human needs and demands.

However, it is also necessary to recognize the significant adverse outcomes of market competition, which include the monopolization of the economy as small producers are displaced by larger enterprises, exacerbation of social inequality, increasing wealth disparity, heightened unemployment, and the onset of inflationary pressures, among others.

Implementing these competitive functions relies on market participants' adoption and use of specific competitive methods. The diversity of possible competitive conditions and circumstances (reflecting the complex structure and operational mechanism of the market as an economic relations system) along with the divergent goals and priorities of competitive actors, which may include profit maximization, market share expansion, or cost minimization, gives rise to a wide array of strategies and methods for achieving success in competitive rivalry. Consequently, competitive rivalry in market conditions acts as a spontaneous self-regulator, maintaining the balance of social production. This self-regulation leads to continuous improvements in economic efficiency, driven by the ongoing intensification of economic relationships and emerging conflicts between the interests of market participants in the exchange of goods and services.

In a balanced market, where prices reflect the socially necessary costs of production, competition imposes stringent requirements on producers. These requirements encompass cost reduction, resource conservation, and labor productivity enhancement. However, market equilibrium, a state where supply equals demand and prices remain stable, cannot be sustained solely through isolated measures, such as price adjustments, innovation implementation, or demand stimulation. Instead, market equilibrium emerges from achieving temporary balance across various levels of economic relations: between productivity growth and household income, across industries, and between consumption and accumulation funds, among others. Achieving this balance hinges primarily on the conditions under which market competition among economic agents arises and evolves, as competition becomes the primary driver of their innovative development.

Market competitiveness reflects the capability and potential of any individual market participant (or group of participants) to influence the terms of trade, particularly the price levels of goods and services. Thus, market competitiveness is defined by the extent to which individual enterprises can exert influence over the market, effectively setting the terms for the sale of goods and services unilaterally.

The level of market competition and overall market competitiveness compel enterprises to seek new forms and methods of competitive strategy, significantly enhancing the efficiency of their production and sales activities. Together, these efforts determine the origin and magnitude of an enterprise's competitive advantages and overall competitiveness.

The synthesis of approaches to defining the nature of competitive advantage and securing sustained competitive positions is a crucial step. It allows for the identification of three core aspects that are paramount in evaluating the prerequisites of competitiveness formation. Understanding these aspects is key to gaining a comprehensive view of enterprise competitiveness.

1. **Competitive Aspect** – Here, an enterprise's competitiveness is determined by the strength of its market position and the effectiveness of its actions within reflexive rivalry against other market participants.

2. **Product-Based Aspect** – This perspective links an enterprise's competitiveness directly to the competitiveness of the goods and services it produces to meet market needs. In this context, competitiveness is viewed as a direct outcome of the product's performance in the market.

3. **Result-Oriented Aspect** – Competitiveness is seen as a comparative indicator, reflecting the difference in resource utilization efficiency between the enterprise and similar entities within a homogeneous group.

Thus, a defining characteristic of enterprise competitiveness (EC) is the degree to which its activities meet a complex set of societal, national, and business-related goals. The need to harmonize various developmental priorities with this complex goal structure necessitates a sophisticated strategic approach to planning competitive advantages at the enterprise level. This strategic planning empowers businesses to identify optimal ways to ensure EC, thereby taking control of their competitive position.

The variety of sources and types of competitive advantages, which serve as the foundation for achieving stable competitive positions, coupled with the complexity and ambiguity of requirements for ensuring competitiveness, leads to a wide array of methodological approaches for evaluating EC (see Table 1).

Table 1

Characterization of the Methodological Framework for Enterprise Competitiveness Assessment

Method	Description of Methodological Approach	Method Characteristics	
		Advantages	Disadvantages
Multiplicative Method	This method assesses enterprise competitiveness (EC) by comparing the baseline and actual multiplicative effects of the relationship (chain) between profit (or effect) and investments in developing strategic potential, product assortment, and ensuring high-quality customer satisfaction.	The method offers relative simplicity in assessment procedures, provides forward-looking analytical insights, and emphasizes a balanced consideration of external and internal factors influencing competitiveness	It faces challenges in objectively defining the baseline multiplier and in differentiating the impact of various factors that influence the relationship between effect and investment.
Integral Indicator Method	The calculation of an integral indicator for the level of enterprise competitiveness (EC) combines assessments of consumer demand satisfaction (product competitiveness) and production efficiency (comparison of the enterprise's performance metrics with those of its competitors).	Clear and visually interpretable evaluation results. Enables the identification of strategic gaps and substantiates effective strategies for enhancing EC.	Challenges in obtaining detailed information on competitors' activities. Requires a substantial volume of calculations and ensuring metric comparability.
Taxonomic Method	This method involves synthesizing assessments of the company's competitive advantages across each product segment in the target market, considering the attractiveness of these segments, including market capacity, growth potential, and other factors.	A comprehensive approach to evaluation, taking into account the significance of both market and production factors in forming EC. Provides forward-looking assessments	Potential difficulties in obtaining reliable information about competitors' activities.
Matrix Method	The assessment of enterprise competitiveness (EC) is based on positioning within a matrix framework that compares evaluations of various aspects of its production-sales activities, production-technology base, competitive rivalry, product life cycle stage, and related factors.	Forward-looking and dynamic evaluation approach. Allows for EC assessments at different stages of the product and technology life cycle.	Inability to obtain precise quantitative assessments. Potential inaccuracy in expert evaluations. Lacks consideration for the relative importance of individual indicators.
Comparative Advantage Analysis Method	Enterprise competitiveness (EC) is assessed by synthesizing comparisons between the company's performance indicators (economic, financial, marketing-sales, production-technology, etc.) and the equivalent (best) parameters of competitors' business activities	Enables the analysis of the interrelated effects of various business activity aspects. Considers the impact of economies of scale. Simplifies the evaluation process and provides clear presentation of results	Static nature of the assessment. Inability to definitively interpret the factors driving the obtained EC ratings. Lacks attention to the influence of external factors.
Method Based on the Theory of Effective Competition	The assessment of enterprise competitiveness (EC) is conducted by comparing indicators of production-sales efficiency, operational efficiency, and financial stability of competing enterprises, as well as with industry averages and benchmarks within the economic sector	Focuses on understanding industry-specific operational characteristics and enterprise development, providing an evaluation of operational efficiency. Offers a comprehensive and detailed assessment approach.	Static in nature. Requires extensive calculations. Lacks emphasis on evaluating product competitiveness. Challenges in synthesizing evaluation results
Benchmarking	A comparative analysis of key success factors (business parameters) of the enterprise and its main competitors to assess the likelihood of the enterprise's success	Dynamic, comparative assessment approach with broad coverage of various business aspects	Ambiguity in selecting comparison enterprises and in defining performance indicators.

	under a specific strategic implementation		
Production Capability Analysis Method	A comprehensive evaluation of the enterprise's strategic potential, based on synthesized index assessments of product quality, cost-efficiency, and production flexibility. This method establishes quantitative relationships among key factors influencing enterprise competitiveness (EC) and models the potential impact of changes in conditions, ratios, or other interdependencies among production factors.	Broad coverage of EC formation factors. Offers a comprehensive evaluation at both the production level and for specific product types. Enables the identification of hidden dependencies and the evaluation of inter-factor influences in production, with an optimization-oriented assessment process	Possible challenges in obtaining reliable information on competitors. Insufficient attention to market factors and characteristics of marketing and sales activities. Inability to account for motivational factors
Product Quality Analysis Method	The assessment of enterprise competitiveness (EC) is based on comparing the parameters of the company's products with similar products made by competitors, while considering a broad range of market and marketing-sales factors	Emphasis on consumer value of produced goods. Hierarchical approach to assessment. Establishes the relationship between product competitiveness and overall EC	Limited applicability in multi-product production environments. Inability to compare assessments of production efficiency
Equilibrium Theory-Based Method	This method assesses enterprise competitiveness (EC) by evaluating the relative cost of production factors (such as loan interest rates, equipment procurement costs, labor wages, and material costs) which, according to market equilibrium theory, should be lower for enterprises with high EC.	Cost-oriented assessment. Broad scope, covering multiple areas of enterprise activity. Forward-looking in its evaluative approach	Lacks consideration of market competition influence. Results may lack precision and clarity. Unable to account for cyclical market factors

Thus, establishing a set of criteria for assessing competitiveness first requires the identification, from the broader pool of market participants (actual or potential), of those entities that meet the following requirements:

Homogeneity of Strategic Goals and Objectives: Enterprises included in the competitiveness assessment set should share similar strategic goals and orientations that guide their economic activities.

Ability to Influence Competitive Conditions: The entities must possess the capacity to impact competitive conditions in the market. Competitive conditions refer to the factors that influence a company's ability to compete, including price parameters, market demand fluctuations, product life cycles (both overall and at various stages), and similar factors.

Uniformity in Consumer Requirements: The enterprises within the assessment set should focus on satisfying consistent consumer demands aligning their operations toward similar market expectations.

Stability of the Competitiveness Assessment Set Across Levels: The composition of the competitiveness assessment set should remain consistent across product, resource-production, and market levels.

Similarity of Geographic Markets and Market Segments: The enterprises should operate within similar geographic markets and market segments, ensuring comparability regarding location and targeted customer bases.

Comparable Market Regulation Conditions: Regulatory conditions should be similar across enterprises, with no participant enjoying artificial advantages stemming

from temporary non-economic factors.

Uniformity of Resource Efficiency Evaluation Criteria: The criteria for evaluating resource efficiency among enterprises (such as the nature of outcomes, effects, costs, and their relative balance) should be consistent. Resource efficiency refers to the ability of a business to use its resources effectively to achieve its objectives. This forms the basis for determining competitiveness levels and identifying competitive advantages for each business entity.

Conclusions. The process of assessing an enterprise's competitiveness is significantly enhanced by the strategic tool of market segmentation. This approach, which involves dividing the target market into distinct groups, serves as a powerful risk mitigation strategy in the face of uncertain consumer behavior. By enabling the enterprise to concentrate its marketing and production efforts on meeting the needs of a specific target group, market segmentation directly contributes to the enhancement of effectiveness. Moreover, it plays a crucial role in managing market risks, such as the potential entry of new competitors and the resulting intensification of competition on the international market. The likelihood of these events occurring can be assessed, with this probability being inversely related to the height of market entry barriers. Higher entry barriers reduce the number of potential competitors, thereby lowering the risk of new entrants posing threats to established market players.

A comprehensive assessment of a tourism enterprise's competitiveness can be achieved by adhering to

these requirements. The precision and adequacy of this assessment are determined by employing a set of local indicators, whose values are subsequently aggregated using methods designed to minimize the influence of subjective factors.

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